

Draft status

As on 16-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to add record of crop image into the knowledge base system.

Steps recommended for collecting crop images:

1. Use Google Advanced Image Search engine to find the image of the crop.
2. Use the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.

Steps for data entry:

1. In the '**Crop Image**' table, find the search box and type the name of crop to be entered. Ensure that there is **NO** redundant record of the same crop.
2. Image of the crop must be uploaded into the Owncloud storage system (<https://www.cropbase.info/owncloud/>) in the folder CropBASE Data > Crop Image. *As of 09-07-2020, the folder can no longer be accessed. Therefore, any online storage system is recommended.
3. Images are named according to their Crop ID. Copy the link of uploaded image stored in owncloud and store the link in the field 'Image URL'.
4. Image size **MUST** be resized to 50kb and the image resolution **MUST** be converted to 550px (Width) x 380px (Height).
5. Enter the name of photographer in 'Creator' field.
6. Enter the name of image provider in 'Publisher' field.
7. Enter the license version of the image in 'Rights' field. Make sure the images are free to use, share or modify and **NOT RESTRICTED** to use by any region.
8. Enter the link of the webpage that provides the image in 'Original' field.
9. Enter the object identifier, the image link from the original source in 'Identifier' field (right click on the image and 'open image in new tab', find the identifier at URL address bar).
10. Include any relevant information in 'Notes' field if there is any.
11. One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID. Refer "SOP - Recording metadata"